

Strong and Δ -Convergence Results for Generalized Non-Expansive Type Map pings through JF-Iteration Process in Hyperbolic Spaces.

A. S. Saluja¹, Aarti Patel²

¹ Department of mathematics, Institute for Excellence in Higher Education, IEHE, Bhopal (M.P.), 462016, India

² Department of mathematics, Babulal Gour Govt. P. G. College BHEL, Bhopal (M.P.), 462022, India

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 20 March 2024</p> <p>Corresponding Author: A. S. Saluja</p>	<p>In this paper, we prove some strong and Δ-convergence results for generalized non-expansive mappings through JF-iterative process in hyperbolic spaces.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Generalized non-expansive mappings, Fixed Point, JF-iterative scheme, hyperbolic spaces.</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of generalized non-expansive mappings was introduced by Hardy and Rogers [16]. Further, generalized non-expansive mapping was introduced by Suzuki's or called condition (c)[29]. It can be defined in many settings of metric spaces. Let $G: Y \rightarrow Y$ be a self-map on a nonempty subset Y of a Banach space X . It is known that if G has a fixed point then G is quasi non-expansive mapping. The class of generalized non-expansive mappings is larger than the class of non-expansive mapping and smaller than the class of quasi non-expansive mappings was defined by Fukhar-ud-din and Saleh [8]. The class of mappings satisfying Suzuki's condition (c) is larger than the class of non-expansive mappings and smaller than the class quasi non-expansive mappings was defined by Suzuki's [29]. The existence and convergence theorems for non-expansive, generalized non-expansive and Suzuki's condition (c) have been studied by several authors, e.g. see Bogin [4], Wong [34], Goebel et al. [10],

Gursoy et al. [14], Gursoy et al. [15], Thakur et al. [30], Dhomphonhsa et al. [7], Ali et al. [2], Uddin and Imdad (a)[31], Uddin and Imdad (b)[32], Uddin and Imdad [33].

Let $G: Y \rightarrow Y$ be a self-map on a nonempty subset Y of a Banach space X and $\{r_n\}$ and $\{s_n\}$ real sequences in $(0,1)$ for all $n \geq 0$. Non-expansive mappings of approximate fixed point for an iteration scheme introduced by Mann [23] which is generated by an arbitrary point $p_1 \in Y$

$$p_{n+1} = (1 - r_n)p_n + r_n Gq_n, \quad n \in Y \tag{1.1}$$

Where $\{r_n\}$ real sequence in $(0,1)$. It is known as Mann iterative scheme which fails to converge to a fixed point of pseudo contractive mappings. Pseudo contractive mappings of approximate fixed point two steps iteration scheme was introduced by Ishikhawa [17] which is generated by arbitrary point $p_1 \in Y$

$$\begin{cases} p_{n+1} = (1 - r_n)p_n + r_n Gq_n \\ q_n = (1 - s_n)p_n + s_n Gp_n, \end{cases} \quad n \in Y \tag{1.2}$$

Where $\{r_n\}$ and $\{s_n\}$ real sequence in $(0,1)$. In the past few decades, large number of iterative schemes were introduced and studied by several authors i.e. Noor [25], S.Agrawal[1] Picard -S Gursoy and karakaya[12], Gursoy[13] and Thakur et. al.[30] respectively, which are generated by an arbitrary $p_1 \in Y$

$$\begin{cases} p_{n+1} = (1 - r_n)p_n + r_n Gq_n \\ q_n = (1 - s_n)p_n + s_n Gw_n \\ w_n = (1 - t_n)p_n + t_n Gp_n, \end{cases} \quad n \in Y \tag{1.3}$$

$$\begin{cases} p_{n+1} = (1 - r_n)Gp_n + r_n Gq_n \\ q_n = (1 - s_n)p_n + s_n Gp_n, \end{cases} \quad n \in Y \tag{1.4}$$

$$\begin{cases} p_{n+1} = Gq_n \\ q_n = (1 - r_n)Gp_n + r_n Gw_n \\ w_n = (1 - s_n)p_n + s_n Gp_n, \end{cases} \quad n \in Y \tag{1.5}$$

$$\begin{cases} p_{n+1} = Gq_n \\ q_n = G((1 - r_n)Gp_n + r_n w_n) \\ w_n = (1 - s_n)p_n + s_n Gp_n, \end{cases} \quad n \in Y \tag{1.6}$$

Where $\{r_n\}, \{s_n\}$ and $\{t_n\}$ real sequence in $(0,1)$. Recently

In 2020 a new iteration process called JF-iteration scheme was introduced by Ali [3] which defined as follow

$$\begin{cases} p_{n+1} = G((1 - r_n)q_n + r_n Gq_n) \\ q_n = Gw_n \\ w_n = G((1 - s_n)p_n + s_n Gp_n), \end{cases} \quad n \in Y \quad (1.7)$$

They obtained some basic properties for Generalized non expansive mappings due to Hardy and Rogers [16]. Also, they proved some convergence results using JF-iteration scheme for Generalized non expansive mappings in uniformly convex Banach Space. Lim [22] introduced the concept of Δ -convergence. Motivated by above, we use JF-iteration process for proving some Δ -convergence and strong convergence theorems for mapping in hyperbolic spaces.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this study, we discuss on the setting of hyperbolic spaces which was introduced by Kohlenbach [19], containing normed linear spaces and convex subsets and Hadamard manifolds [27], CAT(0) spaces in the sense of Gromov [11] and Hilbert ball equipped with the hyperbolic metric [27]. In this context we need some definitions, lemmas and propositions which will be used in the sequel,

Definition [19] A hyperbolic space is a triple (X, d, W) where (X, d) is a metric space and $W: X^2 \times [0, 1] \rightarrow X$ such that $(W1)$ $d(w, W(u, v, \omega)) \leq (1 - \omega)d(w, u) + \omega d(w, v)$

$$(W2) \quad d(W(u, v, \omega), d(u, v, \sigma)) = |\omega - \sigma| d(u, v),$$

$$(W3) \quad W(u, v, \omega) = W(v, u, (1 - \omega)),$$

$$(W4) \quad d(W(u, z, \omega), W(v, w, \omega)) \leq (1 - \omega)d(u, v) + \omega d(z, w)$$

w)

For all $u, v, w, z \in X$ and $\omega, \sigma \in [0, 1]$

Definition [20] A hyperbolic space (X, d, W) is called uniformly convex, if for all $u, v, z \in X, r > 0$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 2]$ there exists $\delta \in (0, 1]$, such that $d(v, u) \leq r, d(z, u) \leq r$ and $d(v, z) \leq \varepsilon r$. Then,

$$d(W(v, z, \frac{1}{2}), u) \leq (1 - \delta)r. \quad (2.1)$$

Definition [20] A mapping $\mu: (0, \infty) \times (0, 2] \rightarrow (0, 1)$ which provides $\delta = \mu(r, \varepsilon)$ for a given $r > 0$ and $\varepsilon \in (0, 2]$ is well known as a modulus of uniform convexity of X . We call μ as a monotone if it decreases with r (for a fixed ε), i.e., for any given $\varepsilon > 0$ and for any $r_2 > r_1 > 0$, we have $\mu(r_2, \varepsilon) \leq \mu(r_1, \varepsilon)$

Definition [20] A nonempty subset Y of a hyperbolic space is said to be convex if $W(u, v, \omega) \in Y$ for any $u, v \in Y$ and $\omega \in [0, 1]$. If $u, v \in X$ and $\omega \in [0, 1]$, then we use the notion $(1 - \omega)u + \omega v$ for $W(u, v, \omega)$. In [20], it is remarked that any normed space $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is a hyperbolic space, with $(1 - \omega)u + \omega v = (1 - \omega)u + \omega v$. Hence, the class of uniformly convex hyperbolic spaces is a natural generalization of uniformly convex Banach spaces.

Firstly, the JF-iteration process is expressed in the Hyperbolic space as follow:

$$\begin{cases} p_n \in Y \\ p_{n+1} = W(Gq_n, q_n, r_n) \\ q_n = W(Gw_n, p_n, s_n) \\ w_n = W(p_n, Gp_n, t_n), \end{cases} \quad n \in Y \quad (2.2)$$

for all $n \geq 0, \{r_n\}, \{s_n\}$ & $\{t_n\}$ are real sequence in $[0, 1]$.

Let Y be a nonempty subset of metric space X . If $G(p) = p$, then p is said to be a fixed point of a mapping G . The set of all fixed points of G is denoted by $F(G)$; $F(G) = \{x \in Y : Gx = x\}$.

Definition [24] A mapping $G : Y \rightarrow Y$ is said to be

- i Non-expansive if $d(Gu, Gv) \leq d(u, v)$ for all $u, v \in Y$;
- ii Quasi non-expansive if $F(G) \neq \emptyset$ and $d(Gu, Gp) \leq d(u, p)$; for all $u \in Y$ and $p \in F(G)$.
- iii [16] Generalized non-expansive if for all $u, v \in Y$ $d(Gv, Gu) \leq a_1 d(v, u) + a_2 d(Gu, u) + a_3 d(Gv, v) + a_4 d(Gv, u) + a_5 d(Gu, v)$ (2.3)

Where a_1, \dots, a_5 are non-negative real numbers with $a_1 + a_2 + a_3 + a_4 + a_5 \leq 1$

C.F Fuster and Galves [9] defined the condition is equivalent to the following condition

$$d(Gv, Gu) \leq a d(v, u) + b (d(Gu, u) + d(Gv, v)) + c (d(Gv, u) + d(Gu, v)) \quad (2.4)$$

For all $u, v \in Y$, where a, b, c are non-negative constants with $a + 2b + 2c \leq 1$ and $a = a_1, b = a_2 + a_3/2, c = a_4 + a_5/2$

iv [29] Suzuki's or called condition (c), which is defined as follows if

$$\frac{1}{2} d(Gu, u) \leq d(v, u) \text{ implies } d(Gv, Gu) \leq d(v, u); \quad \forall u, v \in Y. \quad (2.5)$$

Lemma 2.1 [3] Let $G: Y \rightarrow Y$ be a generalized non-expansive mapping satisfying (2.4), where Y is a nonempty subset of hyperbolic space X . Then

$$d(Gv, u) \leq d(v, u) + \frac{1+b+c}{1-b-c} d(Gu, u); \text{ holds for all } u, v \in Y. \quad (2.6)$$

by [7], We require the following definition of convergence in hyperbolic space which called Δ -convergence. The principle results are obtained by it.

Let Y be nonempty, closed and convex subset of a Hyperbolic space $X, \{p_n\}$ a bounded sequence in X and $u \in Y$, we define a function $r(\cdot, \{p_n\}) : X \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ by

$$r(u, \{p_n\}) = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(u, p_n)$$

An asymptotic radius of $\{p_n\}$ relative to Y is defined by

$$r(Y, \{p_n\}) = \inf\{r(u, \{p_n\}) : u \in Y\}.$$

An asymptotic centre of $\{p_n\}$ relative to Y is defined by

$$AC(Y, \{p_n\}) = \{u \in Y : r(u, \{p_n\}) = r(Y, \{p_n\})\}.$$

The sequence $\{p_n\}$ in X is said to Δ -convergence to $u \in Y$ if u is unique asymptotic centre of $\{p_n\}$ for every subsequence $\{w_n\}$ of $\{p_n\}$. In this case, we write $\Delta\text{-lim sup } n \rightarrow \infty p_n = p$ and call p the Δ -lim of $\{p_n\}$.

Lemma 2.2 [21] Let X be a complete uniformly convex Hyperbolic space with a monotone modulus of uniform convexity μ . Then every bounded sequence $\{p_n\}$ in X has a

unique asymptotic centre with respect to any nonempty closed convex subset Y of X .

Lemma 2.3 [18] Let X be a complete uniformly convex Hyperbolic space with a monotone modulus of uniform convexity μ . Let $u \in Y$ and $\{\alpha_n\}$ be a sequence in $[a, b]$ for some $a, b \in (0, 1)$. If $\{p_n\}$ and $\{q_n\}$ are sequences in X such that $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_n, p) \leq \vartheta$, $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(q_n, p) \leq \vartheta$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(W(p_n, q_n, \alpha_n), p) = \vartheta$ for some $\vartheta \geq 0$. Then, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_n, q_n) = 0$.

3. MAIN RESULTS

First, we obtain the following useful lemmas which help us to prove main results

Lemma 1 A Let $G: Y \rightarrow Y$ be a generalized non-expansive mapping satisfying (2.4), where Y is a nonempty closed & convex subset of a uniformly convex hyperbolic space X . Let $\{p_n\}$ be a sequence generated by (2.2); Then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_n, p)$ exists for all $p \in F(G)$.

Proof:- let $p \in F(G)$ & $p_n \in Y$; since G is generalized non-expansive mapping, we can easily obtain that $d(Gp, Gp_n) = d(p, p_n) \leq d(p, p_n)$; for all $p_n \in Y$ & $p \in F(G)$

Thus using (2.2), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} d(w_n, p) &= d(W(p_n, Gp_n, t_n), p) \\ &\leq (1 - t_n)d(p_n, p) + t_n d(Gp_n, p) \\ &= (1 - t_n)d(p_n, p) + t_n d(Gp_n, Gp) \\ &\leq (1 - t_n)d(p_n, p) + t_n d(p_n, p) \\ d(w_n, p) &\leq d(p_n, p) \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

using (2.2) & (3.1)

$$\begin{aligned} d(q_n, p) &= d(W(Gw_n, w_n, s_n), p) \\ &\leq (1 - s_n)d(Gw_n, p) + s_n d(w_n, p) \\ &= (1 - s_n)d(Gw_n, Gp) + s_n d(w_n, p) \\ &\leq (1 - s_n)d(w_n, p) + s_n d(w_n, p) \\ d(w_n, p) &\leq d(q_n, p) \\ d(w_n, p) &\leq d(p_n, p) \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

using (2.2) & (3.2)

$$\begin{aligned} d(p_{n+1}, p) &= d(W(Gq_n, q_n, r_n), p) \\ &\leq (1 - r_n)d(Gq_n, p) + r_n d(q_n, p) \\ &= (1 - r_n)d(Gq_n, Gp) + r_n d(q_n, p) \\ &\leq (1 - r_n)d(q_n, p) + r_n d(p_n, p) \\ d(p_{n+1}, p) &\leq d(q_n, p) \\ d(p_{n+1}, p) &\leq d(q_n, p) \end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

Thus the sequence $\{d(p_n, p)\}$ is bounded below & decreasing. Hence $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_n, p)$ exists for all $p \in F(G)$.

Lemma 2 A Let $G: Y \rightarrow Y$ be a generalized non-expansive mapping satisfying (2.4), where Y is a nonempty closed & convex subset of a uniformly convex hyperbolic space X . Let $\{p_n\}$ be a sequence generated by (2.2). Then $F(G) \neq \emptyset$, if and only if $\{p_n\}$ is bounded & $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Gp_n, p_n) = 0$.

Proof:- Assume that $F(G) \neq \emptyset$, & $p \in F(G)$, by lemma 1 $\{p_n\}$ is bounded.

Next we will indicate that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Gp_n, p_n) = 0$

Since G is generalized non-expansive mapping, we have

$$d(p, Gp_n) = d(Gp, Gp_n) \leq d(p, p_n) \tag{3.4}$$

from lemma 1 we achieve $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_n, p)$ exists for all $p \in F(G)$

Assume that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_n, p) = \alpha$, $\alpha > 0$. then

$$\begin{aligned} d(w_n, p) &= d(W(p_n, Gp_n, t_n), p) \\ &\leq (1 - t_n)d(p_n, p) + t_n d(Gp_n, p) \\ &= (1 - t_n)d(p_n, p) + t_n d(Gp_n, Gp) \\ &\leq (1 - t_n)d(p_n, p) + t_n d(p_n, p) \end{aligned}$$

$$d(w_n, p) \leq d(p_n, p)$$

Taking limsup as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(w_n, p) \leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_n, p) = \alpha \tag{3.5}$$

From (3.1) & (3.3)

$$d(p_{n+1}, p) \leq d(q_n, p) \leq d(w_n, p)$$

$$d(p_{n+1}, p) \leq d(w_n, p)$$

Taking liminf as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\alpha \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_{n+1}, p) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(w_n, p) \tag{3.6}$$

From (3.5) & (3.6)

$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(w_n, p) = \alpha$, we get that

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(w_n, p) \leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_n, p) = \alpha \tag{3.7}$$

It follows from lemma 2.3, (3.6) & (3.7)

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Gp_n, p_n) = 0$$

Conversely, assume that $\{p_n\}$ is bounded and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Gp_n, p_n) = 0$. Let $p \in AC(Y, \{p_n\})$;

Using lemma 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} r(Gp, \{p_n\}) &= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(Gp, p_n) \\ &\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p, p_n) + \frac{1+b+c}{1-b-c} d(Gp, p_n); \text{ holds} \\ &\text{for all } u, v \in Y. \\ &= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p, p_n) \\ &= r(p, \{p_n\}) = r(Y, \{p_n\}). \end{aligned}$$

That is $Gp \in AC(Y, \{p_n\})$. Since X is uniformly convex, $AC(Y, \{p_n\})$ is singleton, implying that $Gp = p$.

Now we prove Δ -convergence theorem for generalized non-expansive mappings in Hyperbolic space.

Theorem 3.1 Let Y be a nonempty closed, convex subset of X and $G: Y \rightarrow Y$ be a generalized non-expansive mapping which satisfying condition (2.4) with $F(G) \neq \emptyset$, let $\{p_n\}$ Δ -converges to a fixed points of G .

Proof:- It follows from lemma 2 that $\{p_n\}$ is a bonded sequence. Thus, $\{p_n\}$ has a Δ -convergent subsequence. Now, we are going to show that every Δ -convergent subsequence of $\{p_n\}$ has a unique Δ -limit in $F(G)$.

Let u and v be Δ -limits of the sequences $\{p_{n_j}\}$ and $\{p_{n_k}\}$ of $\{p_n\}$ respectively. From lemma 2.2, we have

$$AC(Y, \{p_{n_j}\}) = \{u\} \text{ \& \ } AC(Y, \{p_{n_k}\}) = \{v\}$$

By lemma 2, we obtain that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_{n_j}, Gp_n) = 0$ & $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(p_{n_k}, Gp_n) = 0$.

Next we prove that u & v are fixed points of G & u, v should be unique, since G satisfies the condition (2.6)

$$d(Gu, \{p_{nj}\}) \leq d(p_{nj}, u) + \frac{1+b+c}{1-b-c} d(Gu, u) \quad (3.8)$$

Letting $\limsup n \rightarrow \infty$ on both side of the above inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned} r(Gu, \{p_{nj}\}) &= \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_{nj}, Gu) \\ &\leq \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_{nj}, u) + \frac{1+b+c}{1-b-c} d(Gu, p_{nj}) \\ &\leq \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_{nj}, u) = r(u, \{p_{nj}\}) \end{aligned}$$

The uniqueness of the asymptotic centre implies $Gu = u$. Thus, u is a fixed point of G .

Similarly, we also have v as a fixed point of G

Finally, we show that $u = v$. Suppose $u \neq v$, and so by the uniqueness of an asymptotic centre, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, u) &= \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_{nj}, u) \\ &< \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_{nj}, v) \\ &= \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, v) \\ &= \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_{nk}, v) \\ &< \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_{nk}, u) \\ &= \limsup n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, u) \end{aligned}$$

This is a contradiction. Thus $u = v$. Then $\{p_n\}$ Δ -converges to a fixed point of G .

Next, we prove some strong convergence theorems-

Theorem 3.2 Let Y is a nonempty closed & convex subset of a uniformly convex hyperbolic space X & $G : Y \rightarrow Y$ be a self-mapping satisfying (2.4) with $F(G) \neq \emptyset$. Then the sequence $\{p_n\}$ generated by iterative scheme (2.2) converge to the a point of $F(G)$ if and only if $\liminf n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, F(G)) = 0$ where $d(p_n, F(G)) = \inf \{d(p_n, p); p \in F(G)\}$.

Proof:- Assume that $\{p_n\}$ converges to $p \in F(G)$ so, $\lim n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, p) = 0$, because

$$0 \leq d(p_n, F(G)) \leq d(p_n, p) \text{ for all } p \in F(G)$$

$$\text{Therefore } \liminf n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, F(G)) = 0$$

Conversely, assume that $\liminf n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, F(G)) = 0$ & $p \in F(G)$, from lemma 1 $\lim n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, p)$ exists for all $p \in F(G)$, therefore $\lim n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, F(G)) = 0$ by the assumption.

Now it is enough to show that $\{p_n\}$ is Cauchy sequence in Y Therefore $\lim n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, F(G)) = 0$, for a given $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n \geq m_0$

$$d(p_n, F(G)) < \varepsilon/2$$

$$\inf \{d(p_n, p); p \in F(G)\} < \varepsilon/2$$

In particular, $\inf \{d(p_{m_0}, p); p \in F(G)\} < \varepsilon/2$, therefore there exists $p \in F(G)$ such that

$$d(p_{m_0}, p) < \varepsilon/2$$

Now for $m, n \geq m_0$

$$d(p_{m+n}, p) \leq d(p_{m+n}, p) + d(p_n, p)$$

$$\leq d(p_{m_0}, p) + d(p_{m_0}, p)$$

$$= 2 d(p_{m_0}, p)$$

$$d(p_{m+n}, p) < \varepsilon$$

Thus $\{p_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in Y , since Y is closed there is a point $q \in Y$ such that $\lim n \rightarrow \infty p_n = q$. Now $\lim n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, F(G)) = 0$. gives that $d(q, F(G)) = 0$, that is $q \in F(G)$.

Theorem 3.3 Let Y is a nonempty closed & convex subset of a uniformly convex hyperbolic space X & $G:Y \rightarrow Y$ be a self-mapping satisfying (2.4) with $F(G) \neq \emptyset$. Then the sequence $\{p_n\}$ generated by iterative scheme (2.2) converges strongly to a fixed point of G .

Proof:- From the lemma 2.3, G has a fixed point. Now from lemma 2 we have

$\liminf n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, Gp_n) = 0$, since Y is compact there is a sub sequence $\{p_{nj}\}$ of $\{p_n\}$ such that $p_{nj} \rightarrow p_n$ strongly for some $p \in Y$. by lemma 2.1, we have

$$d(Gp, p_{nj}) \leq d(p, p_{nj}) + \frac{1+b+c}{1-b-c} d(p_{nj}, Gp_{nj}); \forall j \geq 1$$

letting $j \rightarrow \infty$, we get $p_{nj} \rightarrow Gp$. Thus $Gp = p$, i.e. $p \in F(G)$. Also $\lim n \rightarrow \infty d(p, p_n)$ exists by lemma 1. Hence p is the strong limit of $\{p_n\}$. Condition(I) was introduced by Senter & Dotson [29] as a requirement for mapping which is defined as follow

A mapping $G: Y \rightarrow Y$ is said to satisfy condition (I). If there exists a non-decreasing function $g: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ with $g(0) = 0$ & $g(t) > 0$, for all $t > 0$ such that $d(u, Gu) \geq g(d(u, F(G)))$, for all $u \in Y$. Here \mathbb{R}_+ denotes the set of all non-negative real numbers.

Now we prove a strong convergence result using condition(I)

Theorem 3.4 Let Y be a nonempty closed, convex subset of X and $G: Y \rightarrow Y$ be a generalized non-expansive mapping which satisfying condition (2.4) & condition (I). Then the sequence $\{p_n\}$ generated by (2.2) converges strongly to a fixed points of G

Proof:- we proved the following in lemma 2

$$\lim n \rightarrow \infty d(Gp_n, p_n) = 0 \quad (3.9)$$

Using condition (I) & (3.9), we get

$$0 \leq \lim n \rightarrow \infty g(d(p_n, F(G))) \leq \lim n \rightarrow \infty d(Gp_n, p_n) = 0$$

implies $\lim n \rightarrow \infty g(d(p_n, F(G))) = 0$. From $g: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ with $g(0) = 0$ & $g(t) > 0$, for all $t > 0$ we have

$$\lim n \rightarrow \infty d(p_n, F(G)) = 0$$

By applying Theorem 3.2, we obtain the desired result; therefore, the sequence $\{p_n\}$ converges strongly to a fixed point of G .

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Example 4.1 Let $X = \mathbb{R}$ with metric $d(u, v) = |u-v|$ and $Y=[0,1]$ be a non-empty compact convex subset of X . Define uniformly hyperbolic space with monotone modulus of uniform convexity. Let a mapping $G: [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ defined by $G(u) = \frac{u+7}{8}$ for all $u \in [0,1]$. Need to establish that G generalized non- expansive mapping due to hardy and rogers.

Verification: if $u = \frac{7}{23}, v = \frac{1}{8}$ and $a = \frac{1}{2}, b = \frac{2}{5}$ and $c = 0$, we see that

$$\|Gu - Gv\| \leq a \|u-v\| + b(\|u-Gu\| + \|v-Gv\|) + c(\|u-Gv\| + \|v-Gu\|)$$

$$\left\| \frac{178}{200} - \frac{57}{64} \right\| \leq \frac{1}{2} \left\| \frac{7}{23} - \frac{1}{8} \right\| + \frac{2}{5} \left[\left\| \frac{7}{23} - \frac{178}{200} \right\| + \left\| \frac{1}{8} - \frac{57}{64} \right\| \right]$$

$$0.022418 \leq 0.4769014$$

Hence, for $a = \frac{1}{2}$, $b = \frac{2}{5}$ and $c = 0$ ($a + 2b + 2c = \frac{9}{10} < 1$) G is a generalized non-expansive mapping. With the help of manual computation, we compute that the sequence $\{p_n\}$ generated by JF iteration scheme converges to a fixed point 0.99999 of G , where an initial point $p_0 = u_0 = 0.9$ and for all $n \geq 0$, we choose real sequence in $[0,1]$ as $t_n = \frac{1}{10n+2}$, $r_n = 1$ and $s_n = 1$ which is shown by the Table 1 and G has a unique fixed point 0.999999. Which is shown by the Table 1.

Table 1: Sequence generated by generalized JF- iteration scheme

Iterate	Generalized JF- iteration scheme
p_0	0.9
p_1	0.999121
p_2	0.999997
p_3	0.999999
p_4	0.999999
p_5	0.999999
p_6	0.999999

5. CONCLUSION

Our results extend the corresponding results of Ali [3] & P. Chuadchawna[5] in two ways; first, from M-iterative process to JF-iterative process, Second, from Banach spaces to the general setting of hyperbolic spaces.

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“Strong and Δ -Convergence Results for Generalized Non-Expansive Type Mappings through JF-Iteration Process in Hyperbolic Spaces.”

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